

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKPAMOURA****FIRST NAME: ASSE-GNIM RODRIGUE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student used Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6 - 12)
2. Rules for writing a good essay (EUCLID 2021, 12 - 14)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24 - 32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33 - 39)
5. Writing styles (EUCLID 2021, 40 - 43)

THE ACADEMIC WRITING BASICS

1- INTRODUCTION

I have read the ACA-401D course pack as part of my doctorate in international law and treaty law course. I understand that the course aims to prepare me for what is yet to come in my future courses, especially on how to write good academic English. I have found this course pack very useful as it has given me essential academic writing tools. It is even more important for someone like me who comes from a French-speaking country and sometimes tends to keep the francophone writing style even when writing in English. While reading the study material, some concepts caught my attention, and I think a good understanding of these concepts will facilitate my academic journey.

My goal in this first paper I am writing as a student at Euclid University will be to discuss the following concepts: academic essay writing, the general rules to consider when writing, the main differences between American and British English, the notion of plagiarism and how to avoid it and finally the style guides especially the importance for a writer to have his or hers writing style.

2- ESSAY WRITING

It is essential to understand that academic essays are one of many types. The differences between all the existing types of essays will be based on the essay's objective. In the case of academic essays, the purpose of this kind of writing is to provide answers to some questions or hypotheses based on verified and verifiable facts (EUCLID 2021, 7). Therefore, to write a good academic essay, it is vital to go through several steps.

Some of these steps include starting early in the writing process while keeping in mind the question I want to answer (EUCLID 2021, 7). An early start-up will allow me to have the necessary time to collect all the existing relevant data on the subject. It will also help me to draw the skeleton of the work I want to undertake. Once this is done, I will have to collect all the relevant information gathered from the initial readings and take some notes. It is important to highlight here that in the academic essay, these pieces of information must only be collected from academic and credible sources. These readings may be essential later to support my argument. From what I also understand, it is not enough to just read and gather information. It will also be imperative to engage in critical thinking while doing the readings to narrow the scope of my ideas (EUCLID 2021, 8).

The next step in writing my essay will be to organize my ideas by writing a plan I will follow to provide an answer to my research question. Some rules, such as deciding on an answer to my question, selecting the type of evidence I want to use to support my answer, and thinking about the order I want to make my argument, will help me organize my ideas.

These are the essential steps to undertake before starting the writing of an academic essay. The further steps include properly writing the paper with the general basic rules, such as dividing the essay into three categories: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. I will also need to use the appropriate referencing, keep the essay aside for some days, reread it to make sure all errors are noticed and corrected, and then hand it in.

3- RULES FOR WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

The ACA-401D coursepack has also provided me with some basic rules to ensure good academic essay writing. I have found some of these rules very relevant and helpful. Having written some papers in the past, especially when completing my master's degree, I recall feeling lost sometimes because I did not know how to present my ideas and arguments and make them easily read and understood by the readers. I therefore lost much time. I would have saved much time if I had been aware of these rules I read in this ACA-401D study material. Furthermore, I am convinced that my papers' quality would have been much better.

The first rule I have found very relevant is that I should find a way to state the hypothesis in the first lines of my paper (EUCLID 2021, 13). I have found this very important as stating the hypothesis of the writing from the beginning helps stay focused

throughout the writing of the paper. This means that while writing, it will help me continuously ask myself if my argument supports the main thesis I presented.

Another important rule for me is the one concerning generalities. I have used it since high school always to start or conclude my essays with generalities as I was taught such generalities were helping in bringing my subject or point. This way of bringing a subject became a habit. I realized only in reading this study material that this is not an appropriate thing to do, especially in academic writing. The explanation that bringing the topic in using generalities makes it sound like the writer does not know what to say in his paper Euclid (2021, 13) made sense to me, and I understand now that it is better to just to my point.

4- AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

There are many differences between American and British English. Those differences also exist in the academic field. It is thus important when writing an academic essay to choose one of the two styles of English and avoid mixing it with the other. The risk of mixing both types of English is great since the similarities are more important than the differences (EUCLID 2021, 25).

I am more inclined to use American English. This is because I live in North America, even if I live in the only French-speaking province of this continent (Quebec). Once again, as someone coming from a francophone environment, the differences between American and British English are not always noticeable. In French, the writing style is generally standardized in all French-speaking countries.

The chapter on differences between American and British English will be beneficial for me to know the main differences between those two types of English, and this will help me improve the quality of my papers during this academic journey.

5- PLAGIARISM

When I entered university for the first time and started my bachelor, I had no idea what plagiarism was about. To make it worse, nobody taught us about it, as the lecturers assumed we knew what it was. After I failed a paper due to plagiarism, I learned what it was. However, before enrolling in a program at Euclid University, I had never had a proper course on plagiarism and how to avoid it.

Plagiarism is using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). This seems clear. However, I know from experience that plagiarism may be very subtle. Therefore, it is good that the study material explains when to cite appropriately to avoid plagiarism. I understand from my reading that the easiest way to avoid plagiarism is to cite the source of the information I am using in my paper, no matter who or what that source is. The goal is to give credit to those who produced the work because citing the source of information is ethically correct. Thus, to

properly cite, I can use quotations and paraphrases. Using such tools when appropriate will prevent me from committing plagiarizing.

It is, however, also important not to overquote. Doing so in work can rob it of its quality and authenticity. Therefore, in some situations, such as using common knowledge information, it is better to avoid citing as the information used can be found in many different sources (EUCLID 2021, 37).

6-WRITING STYLES

In writing an academic essay, the usage of style guides is practical. Even in EUCLID recommends the Turabian rule style (EUCLID 2021, 41), other styles, such as the World Health Organization (WHO) rules or the Blue Book, can also be used.

Adopting a writing style guide is important for a writer like me because it helps to be consistent in all the papers will have to produce. It is also important to fit in an already existing style. Using an existing style ensures compliance with some basic rules in writing, such as punctuation, vocabulary, font usage, or symbols, for example. It is, therefore, vital that I adopt an already existing style guide and that I write my papers following the prescribed styles. This will help in producing high-quality papers but will also make me save much time in proofreading and corrections (EUCLID 2021, 42).

7-CONCLUSION

At the end of the first period of the ACA-401D course, I understood that producing quality work as part of my academic training for a Ph.D. in International law and treaty law would require me to follow several rules. This course gave me a general idea of these rules and how to apply them. It also allowed me to eliminate a certain fear when enrolling in this course concerning the writing process. I now know that I have this guide at my disposal to lead me throughout this academic journey.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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